

Mesh refinement ergodicity in heterogeneous concrete fracture: a combined virtual - interface element approach

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Abstract

In this paper, an efficient procedure for modeling complex fracture processes in concrete structures is presented that comprises a combination of virtual and interface elements and exploits observed statistical ergodicity. Herein, concrete is modeled as a heterogeneous material comprising matrix and aggregate components. The proposed procedure is motivated by the ergodic behavior exhibited with respect to the configuration of the mesh and of the aggregates. Additionally, the influence of the matrix, aggregate, and interface material properties on the efficacy of the procedure is studied. Numerical results demonstrate that the proposed ergodic procedure represents an accurate and efficient tool for the analysis of complex fracture processes in heterogeneous concrete structures.

1 Introduction

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Fracture processes in quasi-brittle structures, such as concrete structures and components, are difficult to predict as the materials typically exhibit brittle and localized fracture behavior that is highly sensitive to the structure’s geometry and the applied loading conditions. Thus, it is important to be able to accurately and reliably predict these fracture processes to prevent structural collapse. To this end, the development of a model that can successfully predict crack initiation and propagation in heterogeneous quasi-brittle structures remains a critical research objective.

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When modeling fracture in quasi-brittle materials using standard continuum-based methods — such as the Finite Element Method (FEM) with smeared crack models [1] or continuum damage mechanics [2] — mesh dependency is a well-known and persistent problem. Specifically, the predicted fracture behavior is strongly conditioned by the particular discretization of the domain, which can significantly influence the crack trajectory, peak load, and energy dissipation. Furthermore, the strongly localized nature and non-linearity of fracture processes make their predictions particularly sensitive to mesh density and configuration. This numerical challenge is exacerbated by the material’s inherent heterogeneous microstructure, characterized by distinct constituent phases and highly irregular internal boundaries [3, 4]. The spatial mismatch in mechanical properties between the inclusion and matrix phases induces localized stress concentrations and complex micro-cracking topologies, introducing a high degree of spatial uncertainty in the crack trajectory [5].

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Several approaches have been proposed to address mesh dependency in fracture modeling. Non-local and gradient-enhanced damage models [6–8] regularize the problem by introducing a length scale, but they do not explicitly represent the displacement discontinuity across the crack. Phase-field models [9–11] offer a thermodynamically consistent framework and have gained considerable attention, however, they require very fine meshes and remain computationally intensive. Extended/Generalized Finite Element Methods (XFEM/GFEM) [12, 13] enrich the approximation space to represent discontinuities without remeshing, but their implementation is complex and their performance can degrade in heterogeneous media. By contrast, the discrete crack approach [14–17] is a more robust and physically consistent model, as it explicitly represents the displacement discontinuity along the crack and concentrates energy dissipation at well-defined interfaces. To ensure the efficiency of this approach, a numerical method capable of handling complex geometries, irregular meshes, and abrupt transitions in the discretization density is required. In this context, the Virtual Element Method (VEM) [18–24], which permits arbitrary polygonal element geometries, emerges as a particularly suitable approach.

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Despite these recent advances, a significant challenge remains. Specifically, very fine meshes are typically required to accurately predict the crack path which results in prohibitively high computational costs. Moreover, even if computational cost were not

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a limiting factor, the stochastic nature of aggregate distribution and microstructural variability in heterogeneous materials such as concrete means that no single fine-mesh simulation can be considered representative. Different realizations of the same statistical microstructure can yield markedly different crack trajectories, peak loads, and energy dissipation patterns, even under identical loading and boundary conditions. This irreducible variability motivates a statistical interpretation of the fracture problem. From this perspective, ergodicity theory [25] offers a powerful framework: if the system is ergodic, ensemble averages over multiple stochastic realizations are equivalent to the parameter average of a single realization, thus, allowing the overall behavior to be recovered from a representative set of simulations.

Building upon the ergodic VEM–interface procedure proposed in [26] for homogeneous concrete, in the present work this framework is extended to the mesoscopic scale where concrete is modeled as a heterogeneous material comprising mortar matrix and aggregate components. Furthermore, the investigation of the ergodic behavior is extended to consider variations in mesh density, mesh discretization, aggregate distribution, and the influence of mechanical properties. Specifically, the influence of the mechanical properties of the constituent phases and their interfaces is systematically analyzed. While the procedure presented in [26] demonstrated ergodic behavior with respect to mesh refinement in homogeneous concrete — where fracture paths are governed solely by mesh geometry — the extension to heterogeneous materials introduces a fundamentally richer source of stochasticity: the random spatial distribution of aggregates. This aggregate variability dominates the fracture response and introduces a higher degree of statistical dispersion than mesh refinement or discretization alone. The present work addresses this additional complexity and demonstrates that the ergodic framework remains valid and effective under these more demanding conditions. To this end, an accurate and efficient procedure for concrete fracture analysis is proposed that combines VEM and interface elements and exploits the ergodic behavior observed with respect to mesh refinement, mesh discretization, and aggregate distribution in heterogeneous materials. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section 2 the theoretical formulation and constitutive models are presented; thereafter, the discretization strategy and mesh generation procedures are described in Section 3; this is followed, in Section 4, by the presentation and discussion of numerical results. Finally, the work is concluded in Section 5 with a summary of the key findings.

2 Theory and models

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In this section, the numerical framework for modeling fracture in heterogeneous quasi-brittle materials is presented. The formulation is based on a mixed variational approach using an augmented Lagrangian method to handle cohesive interface conditions, following the theoretical and implementation developments detailed in Doyen et al. [27], Labanda et al. [28, 29], and Rivarola et al. [30]. The traction-separation law governing the constitutive behavior of the material components, the spatial discretization via the Virtual Element Method (VEM), and the specific integration of zero-thickness interface elements within the polygonal mesh to capture the discrete fracture process are described in the following subsections.

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2.1 Mixed variational formulation and augmented Lagrangian approach

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In this work, fracture is modeled using a cohesive zone model implemented in a mixed formulation based on an augmented Lagrangian functional, following the approach originally developed by Lorentz [31] and rigorously established in the variational framework of [28]. Consider an infinitesimally deformable body occupying a domain $\Omega = \Omega^+ \cup \Omega^-$, with a cohesive fracture surface Γ across which a displacement discontinuity $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}|_{\Gamma^+} - \mathbf{u}|_{\Gamma^-}$ is admitted. The total potential energy of the system $\mathcal{L}^u(\mathbf{u})$ is decomposed as:

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$$\mathcal{L}^u(\mathbf{u}) = \mathcal{L}^B(\mathbf{u}) + \mathcal{L}^F(\mathbf{u}) \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{L}^B is the bulk elastic potential that accounts for strain energy and external loading, and \mathcal{L}^F is the fracture potential defined through a pseudo-potential $\Psi(\mathbf{u}, \kappa)$ that incorporates a cohesive energy density ψ and an indicator function $I_{\mathbb{R}^+}$ that prevents interpenetration of the crack lips [28]:

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$$\Psi(\mathbf{u}, \kappa) = I_{\mathbb{R}^+}(\mathbf{u}_n) + \psi(\mathbf{u}, \kappa). \quad (2)$$

To account for the non-differentiability of the direct minimization problem, the augmented Lagrangian method of Fortin and Glowinski [32] is employed. A supplementary variable $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is introduced subject to the constraint $\mathbf{u} - \boldsymbol{\delta} = \mathbf{0}$, and the problem is reformulated as a saddle point problem: find $(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) \in V \times W \times X$ such that:

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$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) \leq \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\delta}, \mathbf{l}) \leq \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{p}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}), \quad \forall (\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{l}) \in V \times W \times X \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ are the Lagrange multipliers, $\gamma > 0$ is the penalty parameter, and the functional spaces are defined in the classical Sobolev spaces $V \subset H^1(\Omega \setminus \Gamma)$ and $X \subset H^{-1/2}(\Gamma)$. In [28] it is proven that the Lagrange multipliers carry the physical meaning $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}$, i.e., the interface traction vector.

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The stationary conditions of the augmented Lagrangian yield the following coupled system of equilibrium equations:

$$\mathcal{G}_1(\mathbf{u}; \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = 0, \quad \forall \delta \mathbf{u} \in V \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_2(\mathbf{u}; \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = 0, \quad \forall \delta \boldsymbol{\lambda} \in X \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{G}_1 enforces mechanical equilibrium in the bulk and at the interface, and \mathcal{G}_2 weakly enforces the kinematic constraint $\mathbf{u} = \boldsymbol{\delta}$. The supplementary variable $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is computed in a staggered scheme at collocation points by inverting the traction-separation law locally, following the coordination decomposition method of [32]. The resulting non-linear system is solved using a Newton-Raphson scheme, where the tangent stiffness matrix is split into a constant initialization part \mathbb{K}^0 — assembled once during pre-processing — and an iteratively updated part \mathbb{K}^T that depends on $\partial \boldsymbol{\delta} / \partial \tilde{\mathbf{t}}$, as detailed in [28]. An arc-length path-following strategy based on an energy release criterion proposed in [28] is incorporated to robustly trace the equilibrium path in the presence of snap-back phenomena characteristic of quasi-brittle fracture.

2.2 Traction-separation law

The cohesive constitutive behavior at the interface is governed by a linear traction-separation law that accounts for contact, adhesion, damage, and linear unloading regimes, following [28, 29]. The cohesive potential is defined as:

$$\psi(\delta_{\text{eq}}) = \begin{cases} G_c \frac{\delta_{\text{eq}}}{\delta_c} \left(2 - \frac{\delta_{\text{eq}}}{\delta_c} \right), & \text{if } \delta_{\text{eq}} \leq \delta_c \\ G_c, & \text{if } \delta_{\text{eq}} > \delta_c \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $G_c = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_c \delta_c$ is the fracture energy, σ_c is the critical stress at crack initiation, and δ_c is the critical displacement. The cohesive forces at the interface are driven by a scalar equivalent displacement that symmetrically combines the normal and tangential components of the supplementary variable $\boldsymbol{\delta}$:

$$\delta_{\text{eq}} = \|\boldsymbol{\delta}\| = \sqrt{\boldsymbol{\delta} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta}}. \quad (7)$$

The formulation is extrinsic: the interface remains closed under perfect adhesion until the equivalent traction reaches σ_c . An irreversible internal variable κ controls crack opening and closure, defined as the maximum equivalent displacement up to the current pseudo-time t^* :

$$\kappa(t) = \sup_{t' < t^*} \delta_{\text{eq}}(t'). \quad (8)$$

Once initiated, crack propagation is governed by the damage branch of the cohesive law. Linear unloading toward the origin is enforced when $\delta_{\text{eq}} < \kappa$, and the contact condition

$t_{n-} \leq 0$, $\delta_n \geq 0$, $t_{n-} \cdot \delta_n = 0$ prevents interpenetration of the crack lips. The sub-gradient computation for each loading regime — adhesion, unloading, and damage — follows the procedure described in [28].

In the present mesoscale model, two distinct interface types are defined based on their location within the heterogeneous microstructure. **Mortar-mortar interfaces** are placed along edges shared between two mortar elements, characterized by the fracture parameters $(\sigma_c^{\text{mm}}, G_c^{\text{mm}})$. **Mortar-aggregate interfaces** are placed along edges forming the boundary between a mortar element and an aggregate element, characterized by weaker parameters $(\sigma_c^{\text{ma}}, G_c^{\text{ma}})$ with $\sigma_c^{\text{ma}} < \sigma_c^{\text{mm}}$ and $G_c^{\text{ma}} < G_c^{\text{mm}}$, reflecting the experimentally observed weakness of the interfacial transition zone in concrete [28]. Aggregate elements are treated as linear elastic continua with no internal interfaces, consistent with the assumption of non-dissipative inclusions appropriate for moderate-strength concrete.

2.3 Virtual Element Method

The Virtual Element Method (VEM) [18, 19] is employed for the discretization of the problem domain into meshes of arbitrary polygonal elements. Unlike the standard Finite Element Method, the VEM does not require explicit construction of shape functions within each element, making it naturally suited to handle polygonal elements with any number of edges, including non-convex shapes, hanging nodes, and highly irregular geometries [18].

The problem domain Ω is partitioned into a mesh \mathcal{T}_h of non-overlapping polygonal elements E . On each element, a local virtual element space $V_h(E)$ is defined such that functions are explicitly known only on element edges, while their values in the interior are implicitly defined. A projection operator $\Pi_k^\nabla : V_h(E) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_k(E)$ onto the space of polynomials of degree at most k is defined. In this work, a second-order VEM formulation is employed ($k = 2$), providing a quadratic approximation of the displacement field on element edges. The projection operator is characterized by enforcing:

$$a^E(\Pi_k^\nabla v_h - v_h, q_k) = 0, \quad \forall q_k \in \mathcal{P}_k(E) \quad (9)$$

together with a suitable set of degrees of freedom that uniquely identify $\Pi_k^\nabla v_h$. The local bilinear form is then decomposed as [18]:

$$a_h^E(u_h, v_h) = a^E(\Pi_k^\nabla u_h, \Pi_k^\nabla v_h) + S^E((I - \Pi_k^\nabla)u_h, (I - \Pi_k^\nabla)v_h) \quad (10)$$

where the first term is the consistency part — which ensures polynomial exactness and reproduces the exact bilinear form when either argument is a polynomial — and $S^E(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a stabilization term that controls the non-polynomial modes and is scaled to match the order of the consistency term. External loading terms are treated in a manner analogous to standard FEM [18, 19].

A key advantage of the VEM exploited in this work is its ability to handle Voronoi tessellations — where each polygonal cell constitutes a single element — and the permission

of abrupt transitions in mesh density between different regions of the domain without 184
 requiring graded transitions or special treatment of hanging nodes [26]. This flexibility is 185
 critical in the mesoscale heterogeneous model, where adjacent geometric zones can feature 186
 significantly distinct refinement levels within the same conformal mesh, without being 187
 constrained by the traditional limitations of element-to-element compatibility. 188

2.4 Interface elements 189

Zero-thickness interface elements are inserted along all edges of the virtual elements within 190
 the potentially fracturing regions of the domain, following the algorithm introduced in 191
 [28]. Each interface element connects two co-located element edges with independent 192
 displacement fields on each side, and introduces Lagrange multiplier nodes to enforce 193
 traction continuity in the mixed formulation. The displacement jump \mathbf{u} at any point \mathbf{s} 194
 along the interface is evaluated through a jump operator: 195

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{s}, t) \approx \mathbf{u}^h = [\check{\mathbb{N}}_+(\mathbf{s}, t) - \check{\mathbb{N}}_-(\mathbf{s}, t)] \cdot \{\mathbf{U}\} = [\mathbb{J}(\mathbf{s}, t)] \cdot \{\mathbf{U}\} \quad (11)$$

where $\check{\mathbb{N}}_+$ and $\check{\mathbb{N}}_-$ are the bulk shape functions evaluated on each side of the interface, 196
 and \mathbb{J} is the jump operator matrix that maps the global displacement vector $\{\mathbf{U}\}$ to the 197
 interface gap field [28]. 198

The interface insertion algorithm [28] duplicates nodes along the fracture domain 199
 and assigns independent Lagrange multiplier nodes at each collocation point following 200
 the $\mathcal{P}_c^2/\mathcal{P}_c^1$ interpolation scheme for displacements and Lagrange multipliers respectively, 201
 which satisfies the inf-sup stability condition [28]. In the present heterogeneous model, 202
 the interface insertion distinguishes between two cases; edges shared between two mortar 203
 elements receive mortar-mortar interface elements, while edges at the boundary between 204
 mortar and aggregate elements receive mortar-aggregate interface elements. No interfaces 205
 are inserted along edges within aggregate elements, which remain fully elastic throughout 206
 the simulation. 207

3 Discretization strategy

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In this section, the procedures for constructing the mesoscale heterogeneous domain and its multi-level discretization are described. As detailed in [30], maintaining a uniform, highly refined mesh density across the entire domain is computationally inefficient and unnecessary for localized fracture problems. By exploiting the unique capability of the Virtual Element Method (VEM) to seamlessly handle non-matching meshes and hanging nodes without requiring graded transitions the problem domain is split into two distinct regions: an active zone and a passive zone. This spatial decomposition, schematically illustrated in Figure 1, allows for a drastic reduction in computational cost while fully preserving the kinematic compatibility and physical accuracy in the failure zone.

The active zone corresponds to the geometric region in which fracture localization and crack propagation are expected to occur. Consequently, this area features a higher mesh density and is modeled at the mesoscale, explicitly accounting for the heterogeneous material phases and the nonlinear degradation mechanisms captured by the embedded interface elements. Conversely, the passive zone encompasses the regions expected to remain within the linear elastic regime, which are treated as a homogeneous macroscale continuum. This zone is discretized using a coarser mesh to reduce the number of global degrees of freedom without sacrificing structural constraints.

The generation of initial meshes via Voronoi tessellations, the spatial refinement criteria separating these distinct zones, and the algorithmic selection of specific virtual elements to represent the aggregate and mortar phases within the heterogeneous region are described in the following subsections.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the discretization strategy: example of the highly refined active zone (fracture region with embedded interface elements) and the coarser passive zone (elastic bulk region) within the conformal polygonal mesh.

3.1 Generation of initial meshes

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Initial meshes are generated using a Voronoi tessellation. A random distribution of seed points is generated within the domain. From these seed points, a Voronoi tessellation is created using PolyMesher [33]. A Lloyd-type smoothing algorithm is subsequently applied to generate a centroidal Voronoi tessellation with elements of approximately uniform areas. The initial seed locations (indicated as red dots) and the resulting polygonal mesh are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Once the mesh has been generated, the elements that will represent aggregates are 237
 selected. An algorithm is used to randomly select elements from the mesh that meet the 238
 conditions of not being on the edge of the domain and not touching another previously 239
 selected element. Selected elements may be on the edge of the active zone as long as they 240
 are in contact with the passive zone. The number of elements selected is such that it 241
 maintains a predefined aggregate/mortar ratio. Since the smoothing algorithm ensures 242
 elements of similar areas, we set the ratio of aggregate elements to mortar elements to the 243
 prescribed aggregate/mortar ratio. The final result of this aggregate selection procedure 244
 is also displayed in Fig. 2, where the selected elements are highlighted in dark gray. 245
 Furthermore, in this example, the upper and left-hand edges are considered domain edges, 246
 while the rest of the edges are in contact with the passive zone; for this reason, aggregates 247
 adjacent to these edges are permitted. 248

Figure 2: Sample Voronoi mesh comprising mortar (light gray) and randomly selected 249
 aggregate (dark gray) elements.

3.2 Mesh refinement 249

The mesh refinement procedure proposed in this work aims to refine the mortar region of 250
 the active zone by generating new, smaller elements while keeping the geometry of the 251
 previously selected aggregate elements strictly constant. This approach permits distinct, 252
 uncoupled changes in refinement levels between the mortar matrix and the aggregate 253
 phases. 254

This refinement strategy is a two-stage process illustrated in Figs. 3 and 4. First, the 255
 spatial domain intended for the new tessellation is isolated, as shown in Fig. 3(a); this 256
 target region corresponds to the mortar phase (represented in light gray) and is strictly 257
 bounded by the external limits of the active zone and the perimeters of the existing 258
 aggregates (explicitly highlighted by the red contours). Subsequently, a new random 259
 distribution of seed points is generated. As displayed in Fig. 3(b), these seeds (represented 260
 by red dots) are located exclusively within this light gray mortar domain, adopting a 261
 higher density to achieve a finer mesh discretization compared to the scale of the aggregate 262
 elements. 263

Once the seeding is defined, an initial background Voronoi tessellation is generated using 264

Figure 3: Definition of the refinement domain and initial seeding: (a) isolated aggregate and active zone boundaries (red contours), and (b) distribution of the new refinement seed points restricted to the mortar matrix phase.

PolyMesher. Due to the multiply connected nature of the domain, the raw background mesh does not fully conform to either the internal or external physical boundaries. This geometric mismatch is exemplified in Fig. 4(a), where several background elements either cross outside the designated red boundaries or fall short of reaching them.

To resolve these unshared edges, a sequence of correction steps is performed. First, the background tessellation undergoes a strict trimming process along the exact intersection lines defined by both the aggregate contours and the active zone limits. Then, the original aggregate elements are re-integrated into the arrangement by mapping the projected nodes. This leads to the fully compatible mesh shown in Fig. 4(b), where the aggregate geometry is precisely captured (dark gray phase) and surrounded by the refined mortar elements (light gray phase). Finally, a geometric quality check is executed on the corrected configuration to eliminate non-convex elements and guarantee adequate minimum areas and edge lengths, ensuring the numerical stability of the second-order VEM formulation.

(a) Before corrections (raw background mesh) (b) After corrections (compatible mesh)

Figure 4: Initial versus final compatible mesh configurations: (a) raw background mesh from PolyMesher with theoretical boundaries, and (b) final mesh arrangement with aggregate enforcement.

4 Numerical results

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In this section the methodology and performance of the proposed ergodic-based simulation procedure is demonstrated for the well-known benchmark problem of a 3-point concrete beam with an eccentric notch. The geometry and boundary conditions of the problem are depicted in Fig.5. The geometry of the specimen is rectangular, with dimensions of 400 mm in length and 100 mm in height. There is a central notch with an eccentricity of 90 mm, a width of 4 mm, and a depth of 30 mm. The load is applied through a vertical displacement imposed at the center of the upper edge, while the supports are located 380 mm apart, representing a symmetrical load and support scheme. Plane stress conditions are assumed under quasi-static loading conditions. The region near the notch, where fracture initiation and propagation are expected, constitutes the active zone of the domain, characterized by a field of localized deformations and non-linear behavior associated with the cracking process. This active zone is discretized with finer meshes and cohesive interface elements, while the rest of the specimen, the passive zone, is modeled as a linear elastic continuum with a coarser mesh. The material properties considered are detailed in Table 1.

Three cases are analyzed. First, the geometry and locations of the aggregates will be kept fixed and only the mesh will be refined, to assess the influence of the mesh. Next, the influence of the aggregates will be analyzed by generating meshes in which the positions of the aggregates vary. Finally, the influence of variations in material properties will be analyzed.

Figure 5: Problem geometry and boundary conditions: 3-point bending of a concrete beam with active (dark gray) and passive (light gray) zones.

Table 1: Material properties of mortar and aggregate components.

	Mortar	Aggregate
Young's modulus [MPa]	18500	37000
Poisson's ratio	0.16	0.22
	Mortar - Mortar	Mortar - Aggregate
Critical stress σ_c [MPa]	2.6	1.3
Fracture energy G_c [N/mm]	0.14	0.07

4.1 Influence of mesh refinement with fixed aggregate configuration 298

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The objective of this analysis is to investigate the influence of the level of mesh refinement 300 and the geometry of the discretization when the geometric configuration of the aggregates 301 remains unchanged. The mortar region of the active zone is discretized at different mesh 302 refinement levels and with different randomly generated element geometries while the 303 arrangement and level of refinement of the aggregates is kept constant. The refinement 304 levels of the mortar in the active zone considered are 600, 800, and 1200 elements. These 305 different refinement levels are exemplified in Fig.6. A total of 100 realizations/instances 306 of randomly generated element geometries are conducted per refinement level to assess 307 the variability with respect to mesh configuration inherent in the stochastic simulation 308 process. 309

Figure 6: Fixed aggregate configuration - Different mesh refinement levels.

The force-displacement curves for the 100 realizations at each refinement level are 310 depicted in Fig. 7. The ensemble average peak load and displacement are indicated in red, 311 along with their respective standard deviations. The results are summarized in Table 2 312 which provides the mean peak values and their corresponding deviations. Furthermore, 313 the ensemble average peak load and standard deviation as a function of the number of 314 realizations are illustrated in Fig. 8. It is observed that both parameters converge to stable 315 values at approximately 75 realizations. These results, along with the mean peak loads 316 reported in Table 2, suggest that peak load predictions can be reliably and accurately 317 obtained from ensembles of coarse mesh simulations without requiring very high levels of 318 mesh refinement. Moreover, the results presented in Table 2 highlight that a finer mesh 319 alone does not guarantee accuracy, as the inherent variability of the stochastic process 320

must be accounted for. That is, since fracture behavior is influenced by mesh geometry, 321
a single fine mesh simulation does not ensure accuracy. Rather, the average behavior 322
over an ensemble of varying (possibly coarse) mesh geometries must be considered. While 323
the mean peak loads computed from ensembles of finer meshes do not necessarily yield 324
significantly improved accuracy over coarser meshes, the deviation of the results across 325
individual realizations is reduced. 326

Figure 7: Fixed aggregate configuration - Force vs displacement curves for 100 realizations at different refinement levels.

Table 2: Fixed aggregate configuration — summary of results.

Elements	Mean load [N]	σ_c Load [N]	Mean Disp [mm]	σ_c Disp [mm]
600	68.27	1.653	0.09414	0.007367
800	67.82	1.469	0.09199	0.006209
1200	68.41	1.005	0.09277	0.005789

The crack paths for the 100 realizations at each refinement level are illustrated in 327
blue in Fig. 9. A higher dispersion of results is observed for the case of coarser meshes, 328
however, this spatial variability gradually decreases as the mesh is refined. Nevertheless, 329
the crack paths obtained from coarse mesh simulations are similar to those obtained from 330
finer meshes. This behavior reflects the results presented in Table 2. Notably, the crack 331
paths predominantly follow the aggregate boundaries. This behavior is consistent with the 332
lower fracture energy of the mortar-aggregate interface compared to the mortar-mortar 333

(a) Mean peak load vs number of realizations

(b) Standard deviation vs number of realizations

Figure 8: Fixed aggregate configuration - mean peak load and standard deviation vs number of realizations.

interface.

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(a) 600 elements in the active zone

(b) 800 elements in the active zone

(c) 1200 elements in the active zone

Figure 9: Fixed aggregate configuration - crack paths for 100 realizations at each refinement level.

4.2 Influence of mesh refinement with variable aggregate configuration

In this section the influence of the spatial distribution of the aggregates is investigated. To this end, 100 random stochastic realizations were generated while maintaining a constant aggregate-to-mortar volume fraction and varying the position of the aggregates within the mortar. For each realization, the mortar domain was discretized at three refinement levels—comprising 600, 800, and 1200 elements. Two such realizations are illustrated in Figure 10 where each row represents a unique mesoscopic morphology and the columns

depict the increasing mesh refinement levels. Here, even though the spatial configurations 343
of the phases vary, both the aggregate-to-mortar area ratio and the aggregate size remain 344
constant across all cases. This consistency ensures that the observed variability in the 345
mechanical response is solely attributable to the randomized positioning of the aggregates, 346
effectively isolating the geometric uncertainty from other material parameters. 347

Figure 10: Discretization of the active zone for two different stochastic aggregate distributions/realizations.

The force-displacement curves for the 100 different geometric realizations are illustrated 348
in Fig. 11 for each refinement level. Additionally, the ensemble average of the peak load, 349
displacement, and their respective standard deviations are indicated in red. A summary of 350
these results is presented in Table 3. Although the average mean peak load closely matches 351
that of the case with fixed aggregates (Table 2), this agreement is circumstantial and stems 352
from the statistical convergence of the large sample size rather than a lack of geometric 353
sensitivity. Indeed, the standard deviation of the peak load increases significantly—reaching 354
values around 5.1 to 5.3 for the variable case compared to the 1.6 to 1.0 range observed 355
in the fixed scenario—which represents an approximate three- to five-fold increase in 356
scatter due to the random spatial distribution of the aggregates. These results highlight 357
the necessity of performing multiple simulations with varying aggregate positions when 358
performing fracture analysis. Since the local geometry dictates the failure pattern, the 359
problem exhibits a higher degree of stochasticity than previously observed, making the 360
structural response significantly more sensitive to the specific arrangement of the inclusions. 361

The ensemble average peak load and standard deviation as a function of the number 362
of realizations are depicted in Fig. 12. It is observed that, despite the increased variability 363
introduced by the random aggregate distribution, the ensemble average values stabilize and 364
converge as more realizations are considered. The results further demonstrate that the mean 365
values remain approximately consistent across all refinement levels. This demonstrates 366
that the ensemble average over a sufficiently large number of coarse mesh simulations 367
yields an accurate representation of the expected structural behavior, regardless of the 368

Figure 11: Variable aggregate configuration - Force vs displacement curves for all geometric realizations of different refinement levels.

Table 3: Variable aggregate configuration — summary of results.

Elements	Mean load [N]	σ_c Load [N]	Mean Disp [mm]	σ_c Disp [mm]
600	68.85	5.058	0.08325	0.007069
800	69.16	5.336	0.08988	0.007490
1200	69.33	5.284	0.09024	0.007344

increased local dispersion.

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Figure 12: Variable aggregate configuration - mean peak load and standard deviation vs number of realizations.

The crack paths for the set of 100 realizations at each refinement level considered 370

are shown in blue in Fig. 13. It can be seen that the dispersion of the crack path near the notch decreases slightly with increasing mesh refinement level, however, the overall dispersion of the crack paths in all three cases is similar. This further demonstrates that the results over an ensemble of coarse mesh simulations yield accuracy similar to that of finer meshes, albeit at a much reduced computational cost.

Figure 13: Variable aggregate configuration - crack paths for all cases at each refinement level.

The crack paths for three distinct aggregate configurations, each discretized using a mesh of 800 elements within the active zone, are depicted in Fig. 14. While the notch dictates the exact location of fracture initiation due to stress concentration, the local distribution of the inclusions immediately ahead of the notch tip governs the subsequent propagation path. This direct link between internal geometry and the structural response is further explored in Fig. 15, where these three specific crack paths are superimposed onto the remaining 97 stochastic realizations (Fig. 15(a)), and their corresponding force-displacement curves are highlighted (Fig. 15(b)). Notably, realizations 2 and 3 exhibit remarkably similar peak loads, which differ substantially from the response of realization 1. This similarity stems from the configuration of the meso-structure during the onset of failure; although the global aggregate layouts in realizations 2 and 3 are distinct, both configurations feature a nearly identical clearance distance between the notch tip and the first surrounding aggregates. Consequently, since the crack faces the same initial volume of mortar before encountering an obstacle, the resulting peak loads and early energy dissipation remain highly consistent. These findings demonstrate that the immediate local layout around the notch tip, governed by the stochastic distribution of the phases, is a primary factor driving the overall strength of the specimen.

Figure 14: Fracture paths of 3 realizations with different aggregate distributions with 800 elements.

Figure 15: Fracture paths and force-displacement curves for 800 realizations with different aggregate distributions.

4.3 Influence of variation in material properties 393

In heterogeneous materials, the high geometric uncertainty and variability of the aggregates 394
 can obscure the direct relationship between the material parameters and the overall 395
 structural response. In this section, the utility of an ergodic approach as an effective tool 396
 for model calibration is demonstrated under such stochastic conditions. By shifting the 397
 focus from individual realizations to the ensemble's average behavior, this methodology 398
 filters out local fluctuations to reveal stable statistical trends. Consequently, the following 399
 analysis examines the sensitivity to variations in the mechanical properties, evaluating 400
 both individual and combined parametric changes to isolate their influence on the overall 401
 performance of the material. 402

The sensitivity analysis is performed by systematically modifying the mechanical 403
 properties of both the mortar and the aggregates. Each parametric set is evaluated across 404

multiple realizations with randomized aggregate distributions to ensure the statistical 405
stability and reliability of the results. This approach allows for a clear identification 406
of how individual and combined variations in these components influence the overall 407
response, effectively isolating the impact of the material parameters from the geometric 408
randomness of the aggregate positions. To ensure consistency across the parametric 409
study, a discretization level of 800 elements was adopted for the mortar component. This 410
mesh density was selected to provide a reliable representation of the failure process while 411
maintaining computational efficiency throughout the multiple stochastic realizations. 412

The ensemble average load-displacement curves for three distinct mortar elastic moduli, 413
categorized as Cases A, B, and C, are illustrated in Fig. 16. For each case, the aggreg- 414
ate’s elastic modulus was systematically varied across six different scenarios (1–6). The 415
specific material parameters and the resulting mechanical response for each case-scenario 416
configuration are summarized in Table 4. The results demonstrate that increasing the 417
aggregate’s stiffness does not significantly alter the peak load; however, it leads to a higher 418
overall structural stiffness. Consequently, the displacement corresponding to the peak load 419
decreases as the aggregate’s modulus of elasticity increases. 420

Furthermore, the analysis reveals that variations in the mortar’s elastic modulus (Cases 421
A through C) have a direct influence on the peak load. A clear correlation is observed: 422
as the mortar’s stiffness increases, the overall load-carrying capacity rises significantly. 423
This behavior is primarily governed by the stress state around the notch tip, where the 424
highest stress concentration occurs. Since the mortar matrix is the predominant phase 425
in terms of volume and constitutes the immediate material surrounding the notch, the 426
initiation of the fracture process takes place entirely within this domain. Consequently, 427
the elastic properties of the mortar directly modulate the local stress field triggering the 428
failure, meaning that the initial specimen strength is driven by the constitutive response 429
of the matrix rather than the stiffness of the aggregates. 430

Finally, the parametric investigation is extended to analyze the influence of the mortar’s 431
fracture energy on the overall structural response. The force-displacement curves for all 432
100 stochastic realizations are illustrated in Fig. 17(a-c) for three distinct fracture energy 433
cases: the base fracture energy (G_{f1}), which corresponds to the values defined in Table 1 434
for both mortar-mortar and mortar-aggregate interfaces; a double fracture energy case 435
($G_{f2} = 2G_{f1}$); and a reduced case ($G_{f3} = 0.5G_{f1}$). Throughout these simulations, all other 436
parameters remain fixed. The results demonstrate that an increase in fracture energy leads 437
to a significant increase in the peak load, as well as higher ductility. The results highlight 438
that the fracture energy is not only a key determinant of the load-carrying capacity, but 439
also dictates the post-peak softening behavior. Since the energy dissipation capacity 440
governs the crack path development, its variation fundamentally alters how the fracture 441
path navigates the heterogeneous microstructure, defining both the onset of failure and the 442
subsequent stability of the fracture process. Furthermore, the use of a large ensemble of 443
realizations proves essential in these cases; by averaging multiple stochastic distributions, 444

Figure 16: Influence of the mortar and aggregate Young’s moduli on the ensemble average force-displacement curves.

Table 4: Influence of mortar and aggregate material properties — summary of results.

Case	E aggr [MPa]	E mortar [MPa]	Mean [N]	σ_c Load [N]	Mean Disp [mm]	σ_c Disp [mm]
A1	9250	37000	75.98	5.779	0.07191	0.005740
A2	18500	37000	76.42	5.526	0.06834	0.005245
A3	37000	37000	76.37	5.585	0.06307	0.005017
A4	74000	37000	76.59	5.671	0.05903	0.004747
A5	148000	37000	76.35	5.531	0.05372	0.004463
A6	296000	37000	75.84	5.654	0.04821	0.004642
B1	4625	18500	67.65	5.261	0.01114	0.008289
B2	9250	18500	68.37	5.250	0.10573	0.007433
B3	18500	18500	68.86	5.381	0.09857	0.007496
B4	37000	18500	69.16	5.336	0.08988	0.007490
B5	74000	18500	68.90	5.261	0.07990	0.007170
B6	148000	18500	68.95	5.325	0.07095	0.006931
C1	2312	9250	58.91	4.940	0.17276	0.013394
C2	4625	9250	59.82	5.039	0.16438	0.013452
C3	9250	9250	60.59	5.526	0.15326	0.013179
C4	18500	9250	60.89	5.070	0.13811	0.011778
C5	37000	9250	60.90	4.922	0.12091	0.011049
C6	74000	9250	61.12	4.937	0.10452	0.010341

a more robust representation of the failure process is obtained, effectively filtering out 445
local geometric biases to reveal the true influence of the fracture energy on the structural 446
response. This is clearly illustrated in Fig. 17(d), in which a direct comparison of the 447
ensemble average curves for all three cases is presented. By isolating the mean behavior, 448
this comparative plot confirms that while the peak load scales with the fracture energy, the 449

overall ductility and the stability of the softening branch are also significantly enhanced, 450
 providing a representative estimate of the material's sensitivity to energy dissipation 451
 capacity. 452

(a) Case B4: Base fracture energy (G_{f1})

(b) Case B4-1: Double fracture energy ($G_{f2} = 2G_{f1}$)

(c) Case B4-2: Half fracture energy ($G_{f3} = 0.5G_{f1}$)

(d) Comparative ensemble averages

Figure 17: Influence of fracture energy on the mechanical behavior: (a)-(c) Force-displacement curves for 100 stochastic realizations, including their respective ensemble averages. (d) Comparison of the ensemble average curves for the three studied fracture energy cases (G_{f1} , G_{f2} , and G_{f3}).

5 Discussion and conclusions

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In this work, an ergodic approach combining Virtual Elements with Interface Elements (VE-IE method) was novelly applied to the predictive fracture analysis of heterogeneous quasi-brittle concrete at the mesoscopic scale. This procedure involved the average evaluation of multiple stochastic simulations with different levels of mesh refinement and variations in the configuration of aggregates and material properties.

The results demonstrated that the ensemble average derived from multiple stochastic realizations with coarse meshes provides highly accurate and reliable predictions of fracture behavior. Moreover, the coarse mesh ensemble averages represent a more computationally efficient approach than fine mesh simulations which are still sensitive to the discretization of the mesh and distribution of the aggregates. Thus, multiple fine mesh simulations would be required to generate accurate and reliable fracture predictions at a significantly increased computational cost. It was found that at the mesoscopic level, medium-density meshes with a fixed aggregate pattern yield high precision and low dispersion. Notably, introducing variability in the aggregate distribution increases the scatter of the results—making the dispersion up to three times higher due to the shifting local configurations around the notch tip—yet the collective response successfully captures the structural behavior. These findings indicated that the spatial configuration of the aggregates has a more direct influence on result dispersion than the degree of mesh refinement, thus highlighting the importance of stochastic analysis techniques in meso-scale modeling.

Investigation into the influence of mechanical properties on fracture behavior demonstrated that both peak load and structural stiffness depend strongly on the fracture energy of the interfaces, and moderately on the Young’s modulus of the mortar material. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that the Young’s modulus of the aggregates has only a marginal influence on the overall structural response.

The numerical results demonstrated the effectiveness and robustness of the proposed approach in accurately and efficiently modeling the fracture behavior of heterogeneous quasi-brittle concrete structures. Furthermore, the method shows significant potential for extension to nonlinear problems, higher-order formulations, and three-dimensional applications in the analysis of quasi-brittle materials.

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